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About the measurement of hadronic event shapes for underlying event model tuning with the ATLAS detector at $\sqrt{s} = 7 \text{ TeV}$

Masterarbeit

zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades

Master of Science
im Fach Physik

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(geb. am 04. Dezember 1987 in Ilmenau)

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Berlin, den 24. November 2011

Zusammenfassung

In dieser Masterarbeit soll eine Analyse zur direkten Messung von *Mehrfachpartonwechselwirkungen*, einem Aspekt des *Underlying Events*, bei Proton-Proton-Kollision am LHC beschrieben werden. Hierzu wird ein kurzer Überblick über das empirische Modell zur Mehrfachpartonstreuung innerhalb einer Hadronkollision gegeben. Zusätzlich werden Observablen definiert, für die eine besondere Sensitivität bezüglich der Modellparameter erwartet wird. Die relativen Sensitivitäten werden mit dem PROFESSOR-Programmpaket, welches während dieser Arbeit erweitert wurde, bestimmt. Weiterhin wird das ATLAS-Experiment mit Bezug zur Analyse beschrieben. Störende Einflüsse auf die Messung werden ermittelt und quantifiziert. Hierunter werden Untergrund durch Fehlidentifikation sowie Verschmierungen durch Effekte wie pileup verstanden, welche im einzelnen erklärt werden. Für diese Betrachtungen werden *Monte Carlo* Simulationen sowie im Jahr 2011 aufgenommene Daten verwendet.

Diese Arbeit hat nicht zum Ziel, die Messung mit einer Entfaltung von Detektoreigenschaften abzuschließen, sondern beschränkt sich darauf, die Messung im theoretischen Teil zu motivieren und wesentliche, systematische Fehlerquellen zu beschreiben und zu quantifizieren. Hiermit gewonnene Informationen werden sowohl in der Veröffentlichung der tatsächlichen Messung als auch zur Verbesserung von *Monte Carlo* Modellen verwendet werden.

Abstract

This master thesis aims at outlining an analysis to directly measure *multiple parton interactions*, one aspect of the *underlying event*, in proton-proton collisions at the LHC.

A brief overview over modelling of multiple parton interactions is given. High sensitivity observables for tuning model parameters are obtained with the usage of the PROFESSOR tuning software, which has been improved during the studies for this thesis.

Further, the ATLAS experiment is described. Influences of background to the actual analysis are discussed. ATLAS data from 2011 are used to estimate pileup and QCD background, *Monte Carlo* simulations are used for estimating background from electroweak processes.

Even if this work does not aim at performing the actual measurement, it will give an estimate on systematics noted above, which can be used in the final publication of the analysis as well as in tuning efforts.

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I. Introduction

I.I. Motivation

Even if simplicity is often quoted to be a first indicator of a successful theory, as models evolve, their complexity increases.

In some cases theories, even obtained from first principles, get that complex, that one is not able to predict outcomes of experiments within the framework of analytical calculations, as they simply cannot be carried out. One then starts to build up *Monte Carlo* simulations (MC), which calculate probabilistic approximations of observables.

Another situation is, where no theory can be derived from first principles, thus empirical models have to be created. The nature of those is to include a number of relatively free parameters which cannot be fixed by theoretical arguments.

Also, models are needed when connecting successful theories for different extremal regimes (e.g. high/low energy). In there it has to be defined up to which scale which model is used and how the transition can be made continuous.

The experiments at the *Large Hadron Collider* (LHC, [1]) are particularly interested in hard¹ parton-parton scatterings. These events are comparably rare, but the high luminosity at the LHC will enable extensive analyses of them, which allows for precision measurements of the *Standard Model* (QCD, electroweak interactions and also flavour physics). Also, the search for new physics phenomena is possible due to the high interaction rate. [3]

Nevertheless, only one parton-parton-pair contributes to the hard subprocess. As protons consist of more than one parton, their remnants are able to interact with each other within the framework of QCD. Some of these contributions cannot be calculated by perturbative methods, but are subject to model assumptions. The sum of all additional contributions is called *underlying event*, whereas a certain part of that, the *multiple parton interactions* represent the possibility for partons in the proton remnants to undergo additional (semi-hard) parton-parton scatterings.

The one model we will be interested in throughout this thesis is the *multiple parton interac-*

¹The term *hard* refers to processes in which heavy particles are created or large momentum exchange occurs. [2]

tion. (MPI) model and its implementation in SHERPA [4], a general purpose event generator [2]. It is based on a model proposed by Sjöstrand and von Zigel [5], which will be discussed in section 2.2.

The LHC [1] provides high luminosity and hence high statistics for well understood, hard, electro-weak processes. This should lead to the possibility to search for events with hard sub-processes, remove contributions from them and thus to look into the underlying event directly.

The analysis is performed by a group at the Humboldt University of Berlin, lead by Prof. Heiko Lacker. Results are in preparation.

1.2. Process selection

The purpose of this thesis is to setup an instrument and describe methods to directly measure the underlying event and obtain error estimates for this measurement.

As said above, it seems to be a good idea to look for well understood, primary processes which then can be subtracted from the event record to have a clean look at the underlying event.

For the hard scatter process the production of a Z boson and its decay into an e^+e^- pair was chosen. Arguments for this choice are the simplicity of the final state, a small background from other hard processes, high trigger efficiency for the electrons and clear separation of electrons/positrons from the expected hadronic states from the underlying event.

Additionally, the final state allows for a very precise measurement of the *transverse momentum* of the Z boson ($p_{\perp}^Z$). This observable, $p_{\perp}^Z$, gets *created* during the hard scattering process. And, as there is no initial transverse momentum, a recoil jet has to be created, if the boson should get transverse momentum, to guarantee *momentum conservation*. The recoil jet, however, would disturb the view into the underlying event as they both can look very similar. In order to get the best measurement possible, it is planned to require low $p_{\perp}^Z$ and inhibit recoil jet creation in that way. Events with more than one recoil jet, which would balance out and also produce bosons with low $p_{\perp}^Z$ should be highly suppressed, such that they cannot destroy the measurement.

1.3. Structure of this thesis

After the motivation for this measurement is given, in chapter 2 the theoretical model is outlined very briefly. This also includes a short description of the main tuning parameters² of the MC model. Connected to this, a set of observables is introduced, which are thought to be good indicators for the topology of multiple parton interactions.

To illustrate their *usefulness*, a sensitivity study on generator level³ is carried out. For this task, SHERPA as a MC generator and RIVET [6] and PROFESSOR [7] as analysis, validation and tuning tools are used.

The bigger part of this work contains the experimental side. The ATLAS experiment as well as the run conditions at data taking time will be described in a short chapter, followed by event selection criteria and background studies as well as early comparison plots of uncorrected data to MC simulation. Background and systematics studies are a mixture of simulation based for well understood electro-weak processes as well as data driven and (partly) newly invented methods for QCD background and pileup effects.

²*Tuning parameters* are model parameters, which can be obtained from comparison of data and simulation to make the simulation represent the data as best as possible with respect to the implemented model.

³In contrast to *detector level*, which is the way data is typically recorder, *generator level* represents everything what the event generator created and without resolution effects. To have generated events comparable to recorded data, either latter has to be *unfolded* (see chapter 4) or a simulation of resolution effects in the detector has to be carried out. Typically the second is done to make the first possible.

2. Phenomenological model and event generation

The analysis group decided to use the general-purpose event generator SHERPA [4] for predictions and in a further outlook to tune it to the underlying event measurement, as this is not done for this generator with such a method by now.¹

The basic steps needed to generate an event are outlined in section 2.1. SHERPA aims to make use of modern programming concepts as modularisation, inheritance and encapsulation. Moreover, the basic MC steps are divided into different C++ classes, which allows for a comparably good readability especially for beginners in this field of study.

The respective module for multiple parton interactions included in SHERPA is AMISIC++ [8] which is based on the model proposed by *Sjöstrand* and *van Zijl* [5]. This model is described in section 2.2, following the original papers structure as well as the appropriate chapter in [2].

Observables, which give information about the underlying event, are presented in section 2.3 and classified within a sensitivity study in the last section of this chapter, section 2.4.

2.1. Event generation with SHERPA

In this section, a short overview over event generation in general and SHERPA in particular are given. An extensive source for state-of-the-art general purpose event generation can be found in [2], where many generator authors contributed to and also most of this chapter is taken from.

Typically, it is not beneficial to start event generation with colliding beams and see what's coming out, as interesting processes can be very rare, to the order of 1 in 10^{15} stated in [2].

This leads to building the whole event around the hard subprocess, such that the certain *phases* of the process are connected to the (central) matrix element of the hard process.

The following paragraphs roughly describe these phases and name the responsible module

¹Event generators usually get tuned by their authors to represent data available by time of writing. As event shapes are used here, and obtained from a new measurement, this tuning would be a new effort, as well.

within the SHERPA event generator.

Hard process In the *hard process* simulation step at first all possible *Feynman* diagrams contributing to the given process have to be found and their amplitudes have to be calculated.

The connection between parton level matrix elements and hadron level has to be found by integrating over the corresponding phase space and choosing a suited parton distribution within the hadrons.

The hard subprocess in SHERPA is defined by incoming and outgoing particle states. SHERPA comes with two independent *matrix element generators*, AMEGIC++ [9] and COMIX [10], which are able to produce leading order matrix elements within the framework of the *Standard Model* as well as some extensions beyond it.

COMIX decomposes any four-particle vertex in the processes to three-particle vertices, which significantly improves its performance for large final-state multiplicities. [2]

COMIX performs colour averaging in a Monte Carlo fashion. The colour-flow implementation is especially useful when merging *parton-showers* to the matrix elements, as there is a certain correspondence between some model assumptions in the parton-shower simulation and the QCD results.

In addition to COMIX, PHASIC++ implements the phase space integration for the hard process, given a certain parton distribution.

Parton Shower The matrix element approach (previous paragraph) describes momenta of outgoing partons well, but has shortcomings in representing the internal structure of jets. Additionally to the primary creation of final state partons, these are allowed to emit gluon radiation which leads to showers, as gluons are allowed to radiate gluons or decay into quark pairs, as well.

This does not only hold for outgoing, but also for incoming partons, leading to initial state radiation showers.

In SHERPA, the corresponding module is called CSSHOWER++ [11].

Multi parton interactions and beam remnants The MPI model used in SHERPA will be discussed in section 2.2.

The beam remnants are modelled as a minimal set of particles to reconstruct the constituent flavour configuration of the incoming hadron. Minimising relative transverse momenta of colour dipoles spanned by the outgoing particles leads to colour distribution in the remnants.

As this will not always fit with the primary process' colour configuration, configurations are shuffled randomly until a solution is found. In this shuffling process, the colour configurations of the matrix element are kept. [2]

Hadronization The hadronization module in SHERPA, AHADIC++, literally interprets *clusters* as excited hadrons. It forces most of them to decay in lighter flavours and finally leads to relatively light particles. This is realised by subsequently decaying gluons into quark or diquark-pairs and letting heavy clusters emit gluons. [2]

Hadron decays and QED radiation SHERPA hosts a very large list of decay tables and channels, which are modelled as isotropic decays and branching ratios. Additionally, form factors and spin-dependent matrix elements can be included for fine tuning. [2]

Final state radiation from QED is implemented in the PHOTONS++ [12] module.

2.2. Basics of the MPI model

For the sake of simplicity and clarity one can agree on seeing hadrons² simply as a group of partons, such that a hadron-hadron collision is corresponding to crossings between two parton beams.

As nothing prevents more than one pair of partons to interact with each other, this is already enough to obtain multiple parton interactions within one hadron-hadron-collision. The frequencies of multiple interactions then depend on the cross section of the parton-parton scattering in the two incoming jets σ_{2jets} and the total inelastic proton-proton cross section σ_{tot} .

Sjöstrand and *van Zijl* state the total rate of parton-parton interactions within the crossing of the two jets to be basically described by perturbative QCD, for which the cross section is given to be

$$\sigma_{2jets} = \sum_{i,j,k} \int_0^1 dx_1 \int_0^1 dx_2 \int_{\hat{t}_{min}}^{\hat{t}_{max}} d\hat{t} \hat{\sigma}_{i,j}^k(\hat{s}, \hat{t}, \hat{u}) \cdot f_i^1(x_1, Q^2) f_j^2(x_2, Q^2) \quad (2.1)$$

The symbol $\hat{\sigma}_{i,j}^k$ is used to denote the hard-scattering cross section for the k -th subprocess involving partons i and j . Further f_i^a stands for the parton density function, probing incom-

²*Hadrons* are non-elementary particles. They typically consist of valence quarks and a sea of gluons and quark-antiquark pairs, which are held together by the strong force. Protons, to be collided at the LHC, are hadrons made of three sea quarks (*baryons*). [13]

ing hadron a for a parton i at the scale Q^2 , x_a denote the momentum fractions carried by parton i (*Bjorken-x*). Other variables with hats are *Mandelstam* variables on parton level, for which the following relations hold, given the partons are massless:

$$\hat{s} + \hat{t} + \hat{u} = 0, \quad \hat{s} = x_1 x_2 s \quad \text{and} \quad p_{\perp}^2 = \frac{\hat{t}\hat{u}}{\hat{s}} \quad (2.2)$$

s is the respective *Mandelstam* variable of the hadrons, namely the square of the centre of mass energy.

In words, equation (2.1) sums up the cross sections $\hat{\sigma}_{i,j}^k$ of all possible parton-parton subprocesses and integrates them over the momentum phase space, spanned by x_1, x_2 and $\hat{t}$. The integration is weighted by the parton density functions. The integration over $\hat{s}, \hat{u}$ is implicit, given the relations between the *Mandelstam* variables in equation (2.2). [5] The integration limits for $\hat{t}$, however, have to be fixed. The upper limit cannot exceed $\hat{s}$, whereas the lower could go down to zero. Or not?

To the cross section for parton-parton interactions producing light particles (quarks, gluons, leptons) a term $\hat{\sigma} \propto 1/\hat{t}^2$ contributes [13]. This leads to a divergence, when integrating $d\hat{t}/\hat{t}^2$ down to $\hat{t} \rightarrow 0$. So, for the integration of the cross section of this interaction a lower cutoff has to be defined. As $\hat{t}$ is connected to the transverse momentum $p_{\perp}$, the cutoff also propagates to that, see eq. (2.2). This yields one of the model parameters, which is called $p_{\perp \min}$.

There is no effective transverse momentum in the initial state, hence the transverse momenta of the final state particles is a scale for momentum exchange and somehow the *hardness* of an interaction.

In contrast the total cross section for inelastic proton-proton-collision σ_{tot} can be measured [14, 15] or extrapolated from other experiments [16]. This is a given number, hence there exist $p_{\perp \min}$ such that the parton-parton interaction based cross section of two parton jets (σ_{2jets}) is larger than the total one. This should be interpreted as the occurrence of multiple interactions, such that

$$\sigma_{2jets} = \langle n \rangle \sigma_{\text{tot}}, \quad (2.3)$$

where $\langle n \rangle$ denotes the average of the number of multiple parton interactions per hadron-hadron crossing. It should be kept in mind that the σ_{2jets} and the average number of interactions depend on $p_{\perp \min}$, which means the number of interactions diverges for low $p_{\perp \min}$ in this picture.

The other way around, $p_{\perp \min}$ in the model allows for varying the average number of interactions, thus the number of generated particles in the final state.

This model is only a rough estimate and gets improved by further ideas. First of all, momentum conservation has to be guaranteed. For this, SHERPA (as well as PYTHIA [2, 17]) generates multiple interactions ordered in $p_{\perp}$, so the sum of the x -fractions can never exceed unity. However, this does not seem to suppress the very low $p_{\perp\min}$ region, so another construction - the so called colour screening or saturation - is introduced. This means for the partons to be unable to separate others as independent particles [2], which leads to less interactions. One can estimate the cut-off to be $p_{\perp\min} \approx \hbar/r_p \mathcal{O}(\Lambda_{\text{QCD}})$. However, this seems to be too low when comparing to data. An attempt could be to replace the proton radius r_p by a *typical colour screening distance*, which itself is also not known from first principles and gives a tuning parameter.

A hard implementation of this cut-off with a θ function leads to a large dependence on the parameter and is not preferred. Another method which should smoothly introduce the cutoff is a factor like [2]

$$\frac{\alpha_s^2(p_{\perp 0}^2 + p_{\perp}^2)}{\alpha_s^2(p_{\perp}^2)} \frac{p_{\perp}^4}{(p_{\perp 0}^2 + p_{\perp}^2)^2}. \quad (2.4)$$

This also changes the notation of the tuning parameter, which now is not $p_{\perp\min}$ anymore, but $p_{\perp 0}$. The current implementations in SHERPA and also PYTHIA are done in that way.

By now, we discussed the integration and regularisation of the differential cross section, such that the integral is finite. This integral also incorporates the *parton density functions (PDF)*, which describes the momentum distribution within the hadron.

Moreover, one also needs to account for the matter distribution in the hadrons, to *find* a pair of partons to interact, at all. Models reach from dense spheres over exponential decay and Gaussians to double Gaussians.

The double Gaussians are the current default model in SHERPA, and consist of a dense core and a less dense outer shell. They are described by two parameters in the SHERPA configuration. The widths of these Gaussians are associated with the radii of the proton and the core in impact parameter space. The proton radius is set to 1, such that the *relative core size* gives the relative radius of the core compared to the whole proton. Additionally, the *relative matter fraction* defines the fraction of the total matter to be found in the core modelled by the inner Gaussian.

Initial partons have certain fractions of momenta of their respective hadron, this is represented by the *parton density functions*. Furthermore, they have transverse momenta (*primordial $k_{\perp}$*) of the order of Λ_{QCD} , even if the hadron doesn't have any. These momenta are considered to be normally distributed with a mean and a width, which provides two more tuning variables. [2]

Summary The model proposed by *Sjöstrand* and *van Zijl* is an attempt to describe multiple parton interactions. The framework, as implemented in SHERPA, consists of 6 main free parameters.

In contrast to the description above, $p_{\perp 0}$ is not only one, but two parameters (SCALE_MIN, RESCALE_EXPONENT), which tries to account for energy dependence of the theory. As the SHERPA model is based on the one implemented in PYTHIA, one can assume a behaviour like

$$p_{\perp 0}(\sqrt{s}) = \text{SCALE_MIN} \left(\frac{\sqrt{s}}{\text{REFERENCE_SCALE}} \right)^{\text{RESCALE_EXPONENT}}, \quad (2.5)$$

which is quoted in [18]. Anyways, [18] also shows that the energy dependence is not modelled well. REFERENCE_SCALE, however, is fixed to Tevatron energy (1.8 TeV) by convention. Further it seems reasonable to fix one more parameter and only vary the other to effectively model $p_{\perp 0}$, as $\sqrt{s}$ is constant throughout this exact analysis.

The shape of the hadrons is modelled as double Gaussians with relative core size as PROFILE_PARAMETERS_1 and matter fraction as PROFILE_PARAMETERS_2.

The *primordial* $k_{\perp}$ is modelled to be Gaussian distributed for each incoming hadron with mean K_PERP_MEAN and standard deviation K_PERP_SIGMA separately. But as we consider both hadrons to be identical protons, these parameters shall only be varied in parallel for both hadrons.

2.3. MPI sensitive observables

Bearing in mind that the number of parameters for the model to be tuned is rather large (in total six), we look for a set of observables allowing to disentangle also the parameters (anti-) correlations. So the task is to define a number of high quality observables, which give information about model details on the one hand and which are easy to measure on the other hand.

We will consider events with a Z boson produced and decaying into e^+e^- pairs. For these events, we take out the electrons from the visible final state and define/calculate all observables in terms of the remaining final state.

Some obvious variables are particle³ based observables like the total number of charged particles (N_{chg}), the transverse momenta of the particles $p_{\perp}$ as well as $\langle p_{\perp} \rangle$ or $\sum p_{\perp}$ over all particles. One also might consider observables connected to the Z , such as leading leptons

³On generator level these are characteristics of each particle or the sum of the particles, on detector level one only can talk about *tracks*.

$p_{\perp}$, reconstructed transverse momentum of Z and reconstructed Z mass.

In addition, we will use a set of more sophisticated observables, which allow for describing the topology of the event. These so called *transverse event shapes* have for example been discussed in [19, 20, 21], but as we don't fully comply with them, the definitions used in our work group are given in the following paragraphs.

Transverse thrust, minor The thrust is a measure whether the event is collimated like jets (*pencil-like*) or isotropic in space. A vector $\vec{n}$, $|\vec{n}| = 1$ is searched in the transverse plane, such that $T_{\perp,g} = \frac{\sum |\vec{p}_i \cdot \vec{n}|}{\sum |\vec{p}_i|}$ becomes a maximum. $\vec{n}$ is then called *thrust axis*. Values for transverse thrust reach from $2/\pi$ to 1, where the latter describes a very pencil-like event.

The so called thrust minor ($T_{m,g}$) is calculated similar to thrust but as projection on an axis perpendicular to the thrust axis. Values range from 0 to $1/\sqrt{2}$, where the latter stands for highest isotropy.

F-Parameter Given the momenta of the considered tracks we define the so called *linear momentum tensor* as $\Lambda \equiv \sum_i \frac{\vec{p}_i \otimes \vec{p}_i}{|\vec{p}_i|}$, where $\vec{p}_i$ are vectors in the transverse plane. Further we define $F = \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}$, in which λ_i are eigenvalues of Λ and $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2$. Values range from 0 to 1, where the latter value stands for highest isotropy.

Beamthrust Beamthrust is a sum of transverse momenta which favours central tracks. The formula is given as $B = \sum_i |\vec{p}_i| \exp(-|\eta|)$. Values range from 0 to ∞ .

Sphericity The definition of the sphericity is given as:

$$S_{\perp,g}^{\text{phero}} = \frac{\pi^2}{4} \min_{\vec{n}} \sum_i \frac{|\vec{p}_i \times \vec{n}|}{|\vec{p}_i|^2} \quad (2.6)$$

Values range from 0 to 1, where the latter stands for highest isotropy.

Sum-up In addition to intuitive observables, such as number of charged particles, more complicated ones are added and give in principle a handle on isotropy and topology. It seems reasonable, that high thrust values correlate to low minor, sphericity and F-parameter and the other way around.

Nevertheless, there is hope to find the internal structure of the observables to differ in some cases, so it is possible to discriminate influences of the parameters from each other.

2.4. Sensitivity of hadronic event shapes to MPI model parameters

At first the PROFESSOR toolset is presented, in which sensitivity of observables to model parameters can be measured. Further more, it is defined, what is meant by the term *sensitivity* itself.

The rest of this section presents the setup of a sensitivity study with SHERPA, RIVET and PROFESSOR as well as its results.

2.4.1. PROFESSOR

PROFESSOR [7, 22, 23] was created as a systematic approach to event generator tuning. This tuning can be automatised by defining a goodness-of-fit function⁴ between measured data and Monte Carlo output for different parameter sets to find the optimal one.

As a fitting procedure usually needs many evaluations of the MC response function⁵, depending on phase space of parameters and smoothness of response function, the approach tries to approximate the real MC response by a polynomial of n -th grade⁶.

Even if many MC runs have to be carried out before the approximation can be calculated, the response time for tuning is reduced by the PROFESSOR approach, as (1) the variations can be carried out in parallel and (2) can be used for further inner variations without rerunning the generator.

Also the gradients of the MC response functions are known analytically because of the polynomial approximation, which yields the coefficients.

2.4.2. Definition of sensitivity

A discussion of sensitivity within the PROFESSOR framework can be found in [23].

Assuming the response function of the generator is called R and the sensitivity to the variation of the parameter p is in question, the most natural first approach would be to use the gradient. Denoting sensitivity $\tilde{S}$ leads to

$$\tilde{S} = \frac{dR}{dp}$$

⁴Usually a weighted variant of χ^2 is used.

⁵With *response function* in here the dependence of generated events on model parameters is meant. In the PROFESSOR framework the bin contents of the observables are interpreted as functions of the model parameters.

⁶The original version allowed for 2nd and 3rd grade polynomials, but the algorithms were improved during the work for this thesis to be able to interpolate by arbitrary order.

But this definition would introduce some pitfalls.

First, the absolute value of R is not taken into account. This does explicitly not allow for comparison of sensitivities derived from different observables to decide which to measure.

Second, the same holds for the parameter p , which makes it not possible to compare the sensitivities between different parameters.

A better approach, which accounts for this, could look like

$$\tilde{S} = \frac{|p|}{|R|} \frac{dR}{dp}$$

But on the other hand, this is now biased by a shift in either the value or the parameter. A different *calibration* for the measurement of R , say to measure R distributed around zero, yields different results.

This leads to the point where typical widths w_p and w_R of the spread of the parameters p and the values R can be used to catch these cases. But they should *only* have an influence on exactly this cases, so they get a very small epsilon factor, to really only account when the values themselves approach zero.

The final sensitivity implemented in PROFESSOR is now defined as:

$$\tilde{S} = \frac{|p| + \varepsilon w_p}{|R| + \varepsilon w_R} \frac{dR}{dp}$$

ε represents a small number, to scale this smoothing.

This formula is no holy grail, as examples can be found where other definitions work as good or even better under certain circumstances. But from the point of intuition, this seems to be the way to go.

2.4.3. Calculation and illustration of sensitivity

The sensitivity definitions read like "get the gradient of $\tilde{S}$ with respect to parameter p_i and evaluate this at the parameter point $\vec{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_n)$ ". It is not clear, that the sensitivity to a given parameter is the same at different parameter points.

If the *true* parameter point was known, one could calculate the sensitivity at this point pretty exactly. But, if it was known, one would not need to establish sensitivity to measure this exact parameter point.

So, in case only a broad range of the parameter space can be estimated, some kind of *overall sensitivity* is more interesting than sensitivity at a special parameter point or extremal values amongst all parameter configurations.

Therefore, it has been implemented to calculate the sensitivity at various parameters points and use the median⁷. The *central* parameter point used to calculate the sensitivity at and build a median is chosen to be *default values*, which the generator authors believe to describe data sufficiently well. This is considered to be a good choice, as variations made here are only around the default values, too.

However, to account for anisotropies in parameter phase space, sensitivity with respect to p_i is calculated for multiple parameter points only varying p_i and keeping $p_j, j \neq i$ constant.

2.4.4. Setup

Following software packages have been compiled by hand in order to get the latest versions:

- SHERPA 1.3.1
- HEPMC 2.06.05 [24]
- RIVET 1.6.1alpha0 (svn developer version)
- FASTJET 2.4.3 [25, 26]
- PROFESSOR 1.3.1alpha0 (svn developer version)

Besides installing packages, some lines of code have been written.

First, there is a library (unpublished) which calculates event shapes for sets of tracks/particles with given 3-momenta. Second, there is a RIVET analysis (also unpublished), which was mainly written by *Holger Schulz*, and adopted to the needs of this thesis.

However, the RIVET analysis is preliminary, as it has to comply with the final analysis, which is not written yet. After this has been done, the RIVET analysis will be made publicly available.

Parameter	Default	Minimum	Maximum
K_PERP_MEAN	0.8	0.5	2
K_PERP_SIGMA	0.8	0.5	2
PROFILE_PARAMETERS_1	0.5	0.25	1
PROFILE_PARAMETERS_2	0.5	0.25	1
SCALE_MIN	2.4	1.9	2.9
RESCALE_EXPONENT	0.22	0.18	0.26

Table 2.1. – Generator parameters and their variation. Units omitted, as input files only allow for numerical values.

⁷The *median*. m is an element of a set of values, which it equally divides in two subsets when separating by values smaller or greater than m .

In Appendix A the used SHERPA template file is shown. The variable entries have been randomly filled from a uniform distribution with *prof-sampleparams* (PROFESSOR) according to Table 2.1.

The (processes) section defines the generated process to be initially two quarks or gluons to produce a final state of e^+e^- . The (selector) restricts the invariant mass of the e^+e^- pair to $50 \text{ GeV} \leq m_{e^+e^-} \leq 130 \text{ GeV}$, which includes the Z bosons invariant mass.

To be able to interpolate the generator response function by a polynomial of 3rd grade, at least $\frac{(6+3)!}{6!(6-3)!} = 84$ runs have to be carried out. The recommendation of the PROFESSOR authors is to oversample by at least a factor of 2. To keep the ability to use 4th grade polynomials to estimate uncertainties, it is chosen to run on 300 parameter variations with 10^6 events each.

The RIVET analysis accounts for charged particles with $p_{\perp} \geq 500 \text{ MeV}$ in $\eta \in [-2.5, 2.5]$. The Z selection allows only for decays with an invariant mass between 66 GeV and 116 GeV, following [27].

Photons, which could be emitted due to final state radiation, are not taken into account as they are not visible to the tracking system in the detector later on.

In events with a successful Z selection the leading lepton is required to have at least 25 GeV transverse momentum. For events where $p_{\perp}^Z \leq 2.5 \text{ GeV}$ the measurement write-out of various observables is triggered. As described in section 1.2 the Z boson, being nearly at rest, causes no hadronic recoil, which is needed to have a clean *underlying event* measurement.

The simulations were run on the *National Analysis Facility* [28] at DESY Hamburg and Zeuthen.

2.4.5. Results

Sensitivities according to the definition given in the former section are plotted in figures 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5. In addition envelopes of the variations are plotted. The variations carried out result in a set of bin contents for each observable bin. Ignoring the lowest and highest 16 % of the values, the maximum and minimum of the resulting set are drawn as 68 % envelopes.⁸

From measuring traditional Z variables as its $p_{\perp}$ and invariant mass the overall sensitivity is found to be quite low, see figure 2.1. But there is actually one parameter sensitive in the very low $p_{\perp}^Z$ bin, which is the primordial $k_{\perp}$ for partons inside the hadrons.

Pseudorapidity of particles (fig. 2.2) shows higher sensitivity, especially for SCALE_MIN and RESCALE_EXPONENT. This is expected, as they fix the cut off in the model (see section 2.2) and

⁸Usually variations are given in standard deviations of the normal distribution (68.27 %). But here, no fit to a Gaussian is performed and only discrete values are possible to realise by this method.

Figure 2.1. – Variations and sensitivity for $p_{\perp}$ (**left**) and invariant mass (**right**) of reconstructed Z boson. 68 % envelope of variation (**top**), sensitivity as defined in section 2.4.2 for interpolation with polynomial of 3rd (S_3) (**middle**) and 4th (S_4) (**bottom**) order.

Figure 2.2. – Variations and sensitivity for pseudorapidity of each charged particle η (**left**) and number of charged particles N_{chg} (**right**). 68% envelope of variation (**top**), sensitivity as defined in section 2.4.2 for interpolation with polynomial of 3rd ($\tilde{S}_3$) (**middle**) and 4th ($\tilde{S}_4$) (**bottom**) order.

Figure 2.3. – Variations and sensitivity for global, transverse thrust $T_{\perp,g}$ (**left**) and minor $T_{m,g}$ (**right**). 68 % envelope of variation (**top**), sensitivity as defined in section 2.4.2 for interpolation with polynomial of 3rd ($\tilde{S}_3$) (**middle**) and 4th ($\tilde{S}_4$) (**bottom**) order.

Figure 2.4. – Variations and sensitivity for F -Parameter (**left**) and transverse sphericity $S_{\perp,g}^{\text{phero}}$ (**right**). 68 % envelope of variation (**top**), sensitivity as defined in section 2.4.2 for interpolation with polynomial of 3rd ($\tilde{S}_3$) (**middle**) and 4th ($\tilde{S}_4$) (**bottom**) order.

Figure 2.5. – Variations and sensitivity for beamthrust B . 68% envelope of variation (**top**), sensitivity as defined in section 2.4.2 for interpolation with polynomial of 3rd ($\tilde{S}_3$) (**middle**) and 4th ($\tilde{S}_4$) (**bottom**) order.

thus the total underlying event activity, which is represented by the number of created particles per unit of pseudorapidity directly. Nevertheless, sensitivity with respect to the profile parameters is seen in N_{ch} (fig. 2.2) and also, but less, to primordial $k_{\perp}$ distribution. But considering the measurability one needs to be cautious, because failed track reconstruction as well as tracking inefficiencies can lead to uncertain results, especially in the low-statistics region, which equals the high sensitivity one. This can be seen in fig. 2.2 on the right. The yellow band in the uppermost plot shows statistical uncertainties in the measurement for the central value, the plots below show the sensitivities. For the parameters apart from the scaling parameters sensitivity increases significantly mainly in the low-statistics region.

The event shapes, which have been defined earlier in this thesis, show throughout a good sensitivity for the cutoff parameters and to the others as well, but as seen before mostly in complicated low-statistics regions. Good examples therefore are the tails of sphericity and F-parameter in figure 2.4 as well as the high beamthrust region in figure 2.5.

The strategy for tuning would be not to tune all parameters at the same time. One would probably start with extracting the cutoff parameters from the overall picture and then try to extract the others within their sensitive regions.

Total information about how good a parameter can be fixed would be gained when attempting to tune the parameters to measured data. PROFESSOR and a MINUIT [29] flavour, which is used for the minimisation step, provide the uncertainty on fit parameters, which would show, how sensitive model and observables are. Doing this beforehand, however, seems not appropriate, as uncertainties on data are not known by now.

3. The ATLAS Detector: Design and Operation.

This chapter sets out to describe the detector and conditions used for data taking. As the analysis, which is described in chapter 4, does not need information from all parts of the detector, the description is biased and some parts are omitted.

3.1. Overview

Figure 3.1. – Overview over ATLAS design. Taken from [3].

ATLAS [3] (*A Toroidal LHC ApparatuS*) is a general purpose detector in a barrel shape. It tries to cover as much of the full solid angle of 4π as possible and to give high precision measurement methods. In figure 3.1 the overall design is shown, as well as the dimensions

with 25 m in height and 44 m in length.

The detector is split up in several layers for different tasks to be covered. In addition to the cylindrical, in-out layer structure ATLAS's front and back are closed by so called end-caps. The detection plane of the end-cap modules is perpendicular to the beam pipe and to the barrel layer modules in the central region.

The measurement discussed here selects tracks with $|\eta| < 2.5$ (details in section 4.2), which relies on the inner detectors tracking system as well as the instruments for transverse momentum and energy deposition measurements, in fact the electromagnetic and hadronic calorimeters.

Muon identification and precision measurement is not needed for our analysis, that exclusively uses the e^+e^- decay channel of the Z boson, so this part of the detector will be omitted in the following description.

Official documentation about the ATLAS detector and technical details can be found in [3, 30] and references quoted in there. Condensed to what is needed for the actual measurement, informations from these papers are briefly discussed below.

3.2. Coordinate system and spatial quantities

Figure 3.2. – Shown is a primary, reconstructed vertex and associated tracks. For an additional track, which is well separated, the definitions of z_0 and d_0 are shown. z_0 represents the projection of the point of nearest approach on the z -axis, d_0 represents the projection on the x - y -plane.

The LHC [1] is a synchrotron in which two beams of protons cycle in opposite directions. But it is large enough, that the beam pipes at the position where e.g. ATLAS [30] is situated, can be considered linear. This linear beam pipe is identified with the z axis of the detectors coordinate system. The x axis points to the centre of the tunnel whereas the y axis points upwards, but is tilted a bit with respect to vertical, which is consistent with the whole tunnel being slightly tilted. The coordinate system is right handed, which fixes the positive direction of the z axis.

When it is referred to the *transverse plane*, projections on the plane spanned by x and y axes are meant. ϕ populates this plane and measures the angular distance with respect to the x axis in mathematical positive direction. On the other hand, θ measures the angle w.r.t. the z axis.

The latter is often replaced by the so called *pseudorapidity*, which is defined as

$$\eta = -\log [\tan (\theta / 2)]$$

and populates $(-\infty, \infty)$.

Additionally, for distance measurement the variables z_0 and d_0 can be introduced as shown in figure 3.2. Assuming a vertex in the detector and one track, one can find a point of shortest distance between track and vertex. The distance component along the beam direction is then called z_0 , the radial component d_0 , both *with respect to the vertex*. The track cuts to be discussed in chapter 4 will refer to z_0^{Pri} , d_0^{Pri} as *with respect to the primary vertex*. *Primary* in here refers to the vertex containing the hard process of interest, namely the Z production and decay.

3.3. The inner detector

The inner detector, which is a group of tracking facilities in ATLAS, is illustrated in figure 3.3. It is placed within a solenoidal, magnetic field of 2 T.

A high precision tracking system, consisting of pixels and silicon micro-strips (SCT) covers $|\eta| < 2.5$. The detecting parts are arranged as concentric, cylindric in the barrel region and orthogonal to the beam pipe in the end-caps. Typically, pixel layers get 3 hits per track, whereas 8 SCT layers are crossed per track. The inner-most pixel layer, which is used for vertexing and is directly outside the beam-line, is also called *b-layer* [31].

Further outside there is the *transition radiation tracking* system (TRT), which has a straw tube layout. Their coverage in η is a bit lower, only up to $|\eta| = 2.0$, but they typically get 36 hits per track. Even if the intrinsic precision in the TRT is not as high as in the SCT

Figure 3.3. – View into the inner detector, which consists of a group of different tracking systems. Taken from [3].

and pixel regions, it contributes significantly to the momentum measurement, as the high number of hits and the longer track compensate the single hit resolutions.

Provided with these facilities, the inner detector is well suited for high precision position and vertexing measurements as well as momentum measurement and pattern recognition.

3.4. The calorimeter system

The whole coverage of the calorimeter system, which is illustrated in figure 3.4, is $|\eta| < 4.9$. It can be divided in the hadronic and electromagnetic (EM) substructure, both of them consisting of barrel and end-cap parts.

For the EM calorimeter a coverage of $|\eta| < 1.475$ is designed for the barrel part, whereas the end-caps account for $1.375 < |\eta| < 3.2$). It consists of lead and liquid argon (LAR) and provides, due to its geometry, a complete ϕ symmetry. The thickness of the lead absorber layers is not constant, but has been optimised with respect to the energy resolution as a function of η . The EM calorimeter is also equipped with presample detectors, which can be

Figure 3.4. – View into the calorimeter system of ATLAS. Taken from [3].

used to correct for energy loss of electrons and photons before they reach the calorimeter. The hadronic calorimeter consists of a tile calorimeter and a LAr end-cap. Directly outside the EM calorimeter situated, the tile calorimeter covers the region $|\eta| < 1.0$, with its two extended barrels ranging $0.8 < |\eta| < 1.7$. It consists of layers of steel as absorber and scintillating tiles as detecting parts. The LAr end-caps extend over $1.5 < |\eta| < 3.2$ and overlap slightly with the tile calorimeter as well as the forward LAr calorimeter. The forward, hadronic LAr calorimeter further extends the total coverage up to $|\eta| = 4.9$. The total thickness of the calorimeters is $> 22X_0$ (X_0 : radiation length) for the EM calorimeter, and $\approx 10\lambda$ (λ : hadronic interaction length) for the hadronic one. [3]

3.5. Trigger and Data Acquisition (TDAQ)

Readout of interesting data out of all available information is crucial to the whole ATLAS project.

The LHC and ATLAS operate in a tradeoff region between generating very many events by colliding huge numbers of particles on the one hand but only be able to record a certain

amount of data. Furthermore, the most interesting events are the rare ones, such that an intelligent decision system has to be designed to select these rare events from the bulk to be able to write them to data storage systems. Otherwise both, performance of the readout electronics and detector parts as well as the capacity of the data centres would drastically limit the experiment.

In order to keep the number of *interesting events* - meaning the ones that will be recorded - low enough, a multi level decider (*trigger*) is built up. Functionally, the system can be divided in a low ($L1$) and a high level (HLL) trigger. The latter one is then further divided in $L2$ and the *event filter*.

$L1$ is built with custom electronics and makes, as the name implies, low level statements about the event. Its primary task is to look for high- $p_{\perp}$ tracks, which potentially stem from interesting processes, and measure some basic observables such as missing transverse energy and sum of transverse energy. If the selection is positive (meaning something interesting has been found), the second level trigger is called.

The call of $L2$ includes a region of interest, where to look for the event. This trigger step then reads out all information in the region of interest (about 2% of total event data) and decides on what it finds in there. Finally, the *event filter* inspects the total data for that event and, if positive, the event is written to a permanent storage volume at CERN. The high level trigger system is built on commodity hardware and selections are heavily parallelised.

In this way the event rates are decreased dramatically, ranging from 1 GHz in raw over 75 kHz after $L1$ down to 200 events per second written to disk after the HLL at design luminosity. [3]

3.6. Electron reconstruction and identification

For selecting events with the hard sub-process of Z production and decay, the respective decay products need to be reconstructed and identified. This procedure and its selection efficiency is for example described in detail in [31, 32].

In the central region ($|\eta| < 2.5$), reconstruction of electrons starts from energy deposits in the electromagnetic calorimeter, which is then connected to charged particle tracks in the inner detector. The cluster (energy deposition in calorimeters) search in the electromagnetic calorimeter is performed by a *sliding window* algorithm [32], which scans the area. As stated in the reference, efficiency is expected to be 100% for electrons from Z decays with transverse energy of about 15 GeV. Tracks are loosely matched to calorimeter hits ($\Delta\eta < 0.05$, $\Delta\phi < 0.1$ or 0.05), taking also into account possible losses due to

bremsstrahlung. If at least one track can be matched to a cluster, the reconstruction algorithm reports an electron candidate.

The clusters are then recalculated based on the reconstructed object to take different energy distributions into account in an optimal way. The total cluster energy is calculated as the sum of the measured energy deposition in the cluster as well as estimations of (1) the energy loss in front of the EM calorimeter, (2) the energy deposition outside the cluster and (3) the energy deposition beyond the EM calorimeter. These contributions are estimates which were parameterised, seeded by the measurements in the presample detector (where appropriate) and the different layers of the EM calorimeter. As the parameterisation depends heavily on MC simulation a really good understanding of the detector is crucial for this method.

For central electrons the energy from the reconstructed cluster as well as the direction taken from the tracking system in the surrounding of the matched vertex build up the four-momentum, which is then saved to disk.

The identification process is cut based and relies on observables which are supposed to provide discrimination between electrons and jets, which could look like electrons (*fake electrons*). To have a mutual base for cuts, three combinations have been created, namely *loose*, *medium* and *tight*. The higher level is meant to include the lower level selection and ask for higher quality of tracks, better angular fitting between the layers and further quality criteria. The full list can be found in [32, Table 4] and [31, Table 1].

During the reprocessing of data this identification of electrons is run on any candidate and successful returns are written out in a *list of electrons* to the output file within the ATHENA [33, 34] framework.

As isolation criteria for electrons might well differ from analysis to analysis, they are not implemented in this standard procedure, but have to be applied on top of the selection on the analysis side.

3.7. ATLAS operational conditions

Data used in this theses were taken in 2011 at $\sqrt{s} = 7$ TeV.

Due to constraints in software,¹ only data up to period H (June 2011) is used in the analysis,

¹RJETS and UEINVB are only aware of one trigger setting at a time. In order to gain highest statistics, for each period the lowest, non-prescaled trigger (= records every event passing the trigger selection) is chosen, which has changed in later periods due to different values in instantaneous luminosity. A combination of datasets with different trigger setting is not intuitive in the first place, so one common level was chosen by now. The final analysis will probably include all 2011 data with an overall higher trigger and, again, a common trigger setting throughout all datasets.

which corresponds to $\approx 1 \text{ fb}^{-1}$ of integrated luminosity according to the official *good run list* and luminosity paper [35].

During this data taking periods, approximately five inelastic proton-proton scatterings took place during one bunch crossing (*pileup*).²

During operation and data taking, some issues with the readout electronic of the liquid argon calorimeter arose [31]. Electronic readout for a few percent of cells did fail, when situated in a dead region on the front-end boards. Further more, some high voltage supplies did not work correctly. These kind of events have to be rejected in the analysis.

Additionally, there are some EM calorimeter cells producing high noise signals or don't show the signal expected because of signal in neighbouring cells. This kind of odd behaviour is corrected for by *masking* the cell, which means, in fact, to disregard the measurement in the cell and replace the value by some estimate obtained from the surrounding. However, if this kind of masked cell is in the core of a reconstructed and identified object (e.g. electron), the identification is rejected.

²See the pileup section 6.3 for more information about treatment of this effect.

4. Analysis

The analysis is a multi-step procedure and thus its description is split in *data preparation* and the actual calculation of observables.

The data preparation part includes standard procedures within ATLAS to skim and slim files¹, which reside on the LCG (*LHC computing grid*), in order to decrease the amount of data to download for the final analysis. On the other hand it is beneficial to do the volatile steps of the analysis in a fast-return environment, so running the full chain up to plot-making on the grid is absolutely not suitable for this analysis.

The term *data* in *data preparation* does not only hold for real, measured data, but also for Monte Carlo full-simulation events, which should take all effects of detector resolution and efficiencies into account.²

4.1. Data preparation

For different steps of data analysis within ATLAS there exist different tools and file formats. The analysis at hand needs to incorporate soft tracks on the one hand, and on the other hand a special event selection for Z boson production.

4.1.1. Creating softD3PDs with skim

The current base for analyses to start from is the so called *Analysis Object Data (AOD)* format, in which reconstructed objects from ATHENA are stored within a special ROOT [36] file format. Even if one could access data within this file directly from ROOT, it is of greater use to let ATHENA take care of this data format and write out a more convenient format for analysis. Furthermore, there's very much metadata and unnecessary information in the files, as they are the base for *all* analyses.

¹*Skimming* refers to a preselection of events, whereas *slimming* means to drop certain observables in each event, which are not needed in further analysis.

²At least to a certain extent. As some effects are not fully known until some calibration measurement, it can be necessary to apply correction factors during the final analysis.

In addition to a conversion from *AOD* to *D3PD* (*derived physics data* at a certain level, represented as `ROOT::TTree`) for fast access from within `ROOT` and `ROOT`-based analyses slimming and skimming are performed.

As electrons are already identified and stored separately in the *AOD* file, one can simply ask for them to be present in an event. In here the official *TwoLeptons* skim is used, which requires 2 electrons or muons with each $p_{\perp} \geq 10$ GeV.

Additionally, the datasets are *slimmed* by information not needed for the analysis. For this the official `NTUP_SMWZ` format³ [37] and keep information for soft QCD tracks as well.

These efforts lead to decreased file size down to $\approx 25\%$ in signal MC and even to 2% in data.

Resulting files consist of a `ROOT::TTree` object, which is ordered by events. Branches represent different measurements or signals and can be of simple data types (e.g. `bool` for trigger fired/not) or complex data types (e.g. `STL` vector of `TVector3` for tracks). These information can be accessed from any program linking the `ROOT` libraries and thus *offline* or outside the *ATHENA* framework.

4.1.2. Event selection with **RJETS** framework

RJETS (originally: *WZfratioAnalysis*) is called a *software framework* by its authors and was primarily created in preparation of [38].

It provides a specialised `TSelector` to read out *W* and *Z* related trees from `ROOT` files and operate on them. Additionally, it is suited for producing control histograms and plots in the context of vector boson selection.

For this thesis and the analysis described only the event selection of **RJETS** is used. **RJETS** was originally designed to work with *ATHENA* Release 15 output, but due to the work with *Z* bosons, higher statistics from 2011 data is needed, which only got processed with Release 16 and later. Therefore, **RJETS** had to be modified to output event data for additional analyses to be able to use it. Also, the input data structure for **RJETS** changed, so it had to be adjusted. What is more is that the event selection recommendations by the Electron-Gamma working group changed and had to be implemented.

For each event the following steps are done:

- check for an entry in the good run list⁴
- check that primary vertex has at least three tracks

³A special *D3PD* representation used in vector boson analyses within the Standard Model subgroup.

⁴From a number of quality indicators at data taking time and throughout reprocessing certain events or *runs* might be considered *biased* or uncertain and as such are excluded from the analysis.

- check for LAr calorimeter hole error⁵
- check trigger EF_e20_medium (at least one electron with $p_{\perp} \geq 20$ GeV)
- check whether electron candidates exist
- process electron candidates
 - check reconstruction algorithm (*author*) to be either cluster-based or cluster and track-based
 - check for *quality flags* (booleans from ATHENA indicating data taking complications)
 - electron has to be sufficiently close to the primary vertex ($z_0^{\text{Pri}} < 10$ mm, $d_0^{\text{Pri}} \cdot \sin \theta < 10$ mm)
 - require $|\eta| < 1.37$ or $1.52 < |\eta| < 2.47$
 - rescale energy according to detector calibration
 - smear energy (MC only) to represent data⁶
 - require cluster_pt (calorimeter measurement) to be at least 25 GeV
 - check for isolation: sum of energy in surrounding calorimeter tiles lower than 4 GeV
- check for Z decay products in selected electron candidates
 - require exactly two medium electrons, at least one of them tight and fulfilling isolation criterion
 - require both to have opposite signs
 - require invariant mass of the e^+e^- pair to be between 66 GeV and 116 GeV
- use the T_{Pileup}Reweighting tool to account for discrepancies between pileup in data and MC
- if a Z is found: dump event in even more slimmed format for final analysis

The cuts and quality criteria ensure to only select real e^+e^- pairs and reject fake electrons and electron pairs with a high efficiency and precision.

The result of this R_{JETS} step is another ROOT file in a comparable format to NTUP_SMWZs. In addition to copied information some observables of the detected vector boson are written out, such as the invariant e^+e^- mass, $p_{\perp}^Z$ and electron $p_{\perp}$. On the other hand, trigger information and electronic quality flags are not copied.

⁵The liquid argon calorimeter is reported to have a detection hole in 2011 data until the technical stop. This affects mainly energy measurement of jets. This checkup is a feature of R_{JETS} and done correctly, even if no jets are expected in the considered process. The error is reported as a boolean quality flag in the AOD and also present in the D₃PD.

⁶Although an elaborate detector simulation is carried out, some discrepancies can only be known after taking the data. This correction for example accounts for a residual misrepresentation in the simulation.

The reduction in file size is about 75 % in MC and more than 99 % in data, where this is not only due to slimming but also due to event selection.

The ability to produce these files with a stable and generous event selection, which allows for cut variations in the last step, on the grid and thus only require to download comparably small files is a huge gain. Another benefit is then the ability to quickly create final histograms and plots from the RJETS' output files, which is the topic of the following section.

4.2. UEINVB - the analysis itself

From a structural point of view UEINVB (*Underlying Event in Vector Boson production*) is similar to the RJETS framework.

It inherits from TSelector and links to ROOT. For reading the input files into C++ objects it uses the *D3PDMakerReader* package [39] and also utilises a histogram booking, which was originally developed within RJETS. The histogram booking allows for creation of sets of histograms with same *base name* but different pre- and suffices, to allow for easy adoption in systematic studies⁷ and similar.

UEINVB is, as the name tells, not only suited for a Z analysis but also for a W analysis. Only one process, however, should be analysed at a time. Hence, UEINVB is checking first for the detected process and rejecting the wrong type.

As UEINVB is the main part of the analysis and it is thought that bundling all core parts in a monolithic package is a good idea throughout the analysis group, it supports running various systematics studies from the same source base as it iterates over sets of cut parameters and manipulation functions. For illustrational purpose, the nominal analysis, which is outlined in figure 4.1, will be described.

UEINVB goes through the RJETS output and checks the events to be of the correct process type. Technically, this is implemented as check for the second leptons charge, which is 0 for a neutrino in W decay and ± 1 for Z decay.

After that, the control flow reaches a systematics loop. For each event, the analysis is performed for each enabled systematic. First things done within the loop are the setup of 'what has to be done', or simply nothing for the nominal run. This setup step is followed by reconstructing the vector boson directly from the two leptons, their momenta are stored in RJETS' output.⁸

Relying on the vertexing algorithm in ATHENA in the first place, each vertex, which got

⁷*Systematic* represents all kind of variations one can think of applying to the data. This can be adding tracks from *secondaries* or pileup as well as deleting tracks due to efficiencies.

⁸RJETS output is a TTree and the selected lepton properties are stored as additional branches.

Figure 4.1. – Overview over UEINVBs internal processing of RJEts' output files. Output are 1D- and 2D-histograms in ROOT format for plotting or further usage.

reconstructed as *primary* (type 1) or *pileup* (type 3) is analysed separately. For the measurement, only the primary vertex counts, but to discriminate their characteristics from pileup vertices, this step is important. Inside the vertex-loop we face another iterative code block, which scans through all adjacent tracks of the vertex and performs the *track selection* step. In there, some quality criteria and phase space cuts as well as the requirements to be close enough to the vertex in question are applied.

The track selection part generates a vector (std::vector) of selected tracks.

After the vertex analysis, observables (e.g. event shapes) are calculated (using the selected final state tracks) and stored in a ROOT file.

If the sample is a Monte Carlo simulation sample, *truth*⁹ information is stored in the input files and can be used to calculate *truth* observables. This is important to estimate influence of detector and reconstruction on the variables.

With truth information also histograms are filled and, in addition, smearing histograms (2D) are created. These 2D histograms represent the *true* value on the one and the *measured* value on the other axis, illustrating the transition between both.

The last procedure shown in the control flow diagram, named *various control histograms* is a condensed version, as the control plots are made between each two steps, when applicable.

All histogram filling also accounts for event weights differing from 1, which can be caused by pileup reweighing¹⁰ or weighted event generation¹¹.

As described earlier, this analysis can run with different cut variables and systematics.

Systematics built in so far are:

PileUp (data driven estimation, see section 6.3)

- build pileup vertex library¹²
- merge primary vertex with random pileup from library
- ⇒ effectively append tracks to selected track vector

Tracking efficiency variation

- choose within *nominal*, *higher*- and *lower-than-nominal* efficiency

⁹Generator output without detector simulation is referred to as *truth*. This is the same information level as used in the RIVET analysis in section 2.4.

¹⁰MC samples with full detector simulation are produced with a certain average number of simultaneous interactions. But to account for the actual situation in data, events are reweighed to represent data even better.

¹¹This is done to improve statistics for rare processes or phase space areas. More events are generated in these areas but get a lower event weight each.

¹²Tracks, represented by their reconstructed 3-vector, are stored in a TTree. An entry in the tree does not only represent one track, but a list of tracks coming from one vertex. The vertices used here are selected to be far away from the primary vertex ($\Delta z \geq 10$ mm) and reconstructed as pileup vertices.

⇒ randomly delete tracks from selected track vector

Track $p_{\perp}$ smearing

- define width of Gaussian smearing
- apply Gaussian smearing to track $p_{\perp}$

Each of the systematics populate a `TDirectory` within the output `Root` file with all histograms present in the nominal analysis and smearing histograms, showing the migration between the nominal analysis and the given systematic.

4.3. Further steps in analysis

Now that the analysis software is mainly set up, a procedure to obtain results is briefly outlined.

First, uncorrected data are compared to MC after full simulation (chapter 5).

Afterwards, influences of analysis cuts have to be studied.¹³ This can be done by varying them over a reasonable range and check for the number of events passing cuts and also how final observables change. Efficiencies provided centrally by *combined performance groups* [31] should be used to estimate uncertainties on final observables.

This is followed by the estimation of backgrounds (chapter 6). Doing this, one has to decide whether they provide *corrections* or *systematics*, where former actually change the measured data points and latter only increase the error band around them. Within this chapter, also the pileup problem is discussed and some possibilities for corrections are outlined.

One also has to *unfold* data, which means propagate final events backwards through the detector.¹³ This can be done in various ways, beginning from bin-to-bin correction factors up to application of *Bayes' Theorem*. [40]

Also, a suitable way for propagating errors through this whole chain has to be found.

¹³This is not performed in this thesis.

5. Measurement of uncorrected data

After the description of the analysis procedure and having built the analysis software, it is possible to plot raw data and MC observables. This means, no correction in any sense is applied to data, only the selection described earlier is done. Plots should be merely considered a *proof of concept*, not the result of a *real* measurement.

Run Number	Event generator	Pileup	Generated Events
119126	SHERPA	Yes	1998595
106087	MC@NLO [41] + Herwig [42, 43] + Jimmy[44]	Yes	4996184
106046	PYTHIA 6	Yes	4999076
106046	PYTHIA 6	No	4999076
126184	PYTHIA 8	No	4999348

Table 5.1. – List of Monte Carlo samples used in the analysis. *Pileup* indicates, whether hits from a sample, which is meant to represent pileup vertices, are added after the detector simulation in order to disturb the reconstruction the way data would be affected by pileup.

Data taken between February and June 2011, corresponding to $\approx 1.06 \text{ fb}^{-1}$ and internally called periods B, D, E, F, G, H, is compared to simulated events. The Monte Carlo samples used, representing Z production in proton-proton collisions and later on decay into e^+e^- , are listed in table 5.1.

Although it was discussed in the first chapters that SHERPA should be used to study underlying event model variations, other generators are plotted and processed for comparison on the one hand, also to have more statistics for detector unfolding in the long term on the other hand.

Observables on reconstruction level can be found in figure 5.1 without a cut on transverse Z momentum and in figure 5.2 requiring $p_{\perp}^Z < 3 \text{ GeV}$ in order to suppress recoil activity. The final cut also has to represent the measurement uncertainty, so it is possible that it gets loosened.

The basic event features are found to be in agreement between the generators and data. This can be seen for example in the invariant mass of the reconstructed Z boson (respectively the reconstructed and selected e^+e^- pair) and around the peaks of the event shapes. Also the shape of the pseudorapidity matches, however, total activity varies between the generators.

Figure 5.1. – Uncorrected data and MC with detector simulation after reconstruction and track selection described in chapter 4. Tracks are required to be in the inner detector $|\eta| < 2.5$ and to have at least $p_{\perp} = 0.5$ GeV. Also, all plots apart from N_{trk} require at least two tracks. No cuts on $p_{\perp}^Z$ applied. Uncertainties are statistical only.

Figure 5.2. – Uncorrected data and MC with detector simulation after reconstruction and track selection described in chapter 4. Tracks are required to be in the inner detector $|\eta| < 2.5$ and to have at least $p_{\perp} = 0.5 \text{ GeV}$. Also, all plots apart from N_{trk} require at least two tracks. $p_{\perp}^Z < 3 \text{ GeV}$ required. Uncertainties are statistical only.

Figure 5.3. – N_{trk} after selection in data (**left**) and simulation (SHERPA, **right**) for various slices in $p_{\perp}^Z$. Black line represents the sum of all slices inclusively. A larger disagreement for lower $p_{\perp}^Z$ is observed. Uncertainties are statistical only.

What is more of a concern is the disagreement in extremal values. One finds low N_{trk} to be not well described by any of the generators. This also seems to correspond to higher thrust values and lower sphericity and F-Parameter, where the yield is overestimated by the generators. Provided, in an event only two additional tracks, that pass the selection, are created. Momentum conservation and that additional tracks, which don't pass the selection carry non-significant momenta, the both should go back-to-back due to momentum conservation. This leads to a thrust value near 1, which also corresponds to low $S_{\perp,g}^{\text{phero}}$ and F .

In figure 5.3, we also find an indication for MPI models to simply *fail* under certain circumstances, and this is also independent from the exact model implemented. In figure 5.3 we see that the disagreement seems to worsen when approaching low $p_{\perp}^Z$ values. This might give hints to generator authors to implement different models.

Although these plots look quite persuasive, one needs to be careful, as there is absolutely no knowledge about the source of the disagreement, and also why no one before found this. However, the peaking structure is present in MC truth and expected by MC authors.¹ In addition to the MPI model the proton remnants are connected by a coloured *Lund* string, which eventually breaks up and hadronises. The peaking structure seems to be related to the string in events where no MPI is triggered.

However, also on the analysis side cross checks have to be made to exclude mistakes.

¹Private communication with F. Krauss.

6. Estimation of backgrounds and systematics

In this thesis only a selection of studies of this part of the analysis are performed.

This chapter illustrates the influence of electroweak processes (6.1) and QCD processes (6.2), which could lead to false positive Z identification.

Finally, pileup, its influence on the observables as well as correction strategies are discussed (6.3).

6.1. Estimation of background from electroweak processes

Electroweak processes are mostly well understood and modelled in Monte Carlo simulation programs. That's why simulation samples can be used to determine cut efficiencies for the primary process and to check for false positives.

In the following paragraphs, the background contributions from electroweak processes are described.

W decaying to $e\nu$ As Z can be produced in proton-proton collisions, W can, too. Even if the direct decay product of the W might merely be visible as Z candidate, a hadronic recoil might fake a positron (or electron) signature and, together with the real electron (or positron) be reconstructed as a Z candidate. This might be rare, but has to be considered as the cross section of W production is one magnitude larger than Z production.

Heavy quark pair production ($t\bar{t}$) During a proton-proton collision it is possible to create a pair of heavy quarks. Of them, the $t\bar{t}$ pair is able to decay into leptons through W production/decay. In this process, e^-/e^+ might be directly or indirectly produced (mediated by a τ). Under some circumstances they can fulfil selection criteria and might get reconstructed as a Z candidate.

Figure 6.1. – Comparison between data and MC (signal and backgrounds) as well as background estimation for QCD. QCD estimated from invariant mass sideband. MC are scaled to expected event counts in data taking luminosity of 1.06 fb^{-1} .

Z decaying to $\tau^+\tau^-$ Also, a Z might not decay into an e^+e^- pair, but into two tauons. These will decay later on and apparently create e^+e^- pairs (or fakes), which then might be reconstructed as Z candidate.

Diboson production Another source of electroweak backgrounds is diboson production. In here W^+W^- , ZZ or $W^\pm Z$ are created and decay leptonically. The decay products may be reconstructed as one (and only one) Z candidate.

To estimate the influence of these processes on our measurement, Sherpa samples listed in table 6.1 are used.

Run Number	Process	Sample Size	Scaling Factor
117800	$t\bar{t} \rightarrow l^+l^- + X$	149882	$3.41 \cdot 10^{-2}$
119128	$W^\pm \rightarrow e^\pm\nu$	1699637	5.46
119931	$Z \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$	159947	6.53
126045	$W^+W^- \rightarrow l\nu l\nu$	499911	$7.46 \cdot 10^{-3}$
126049	$W^\pm Z \rightarrow l^\pm\nu l^+l^-$	499889	$9.09 \cdot 10^{-4}$
126148	$ZZ \rightarrow 4l$	499847	$2.51 \cdot 10^{-4}$
126153	$ZZ \rightarrow l^+l^-\nu\nu$	499888	$4.87 \cdot 10^{-4}$

Table 6.1. – Full simulation SHERPA samples for electroweak background estimation. All analysed as described in section 4.

Results are shown in figure 6.1. The MC samples are scaled to recorded, integrated luminosity $\mathcal{L}$ in data.

Given the nominal sample size is N and the process' cross section is σ , a scale factor of $\sigma \cdot \mathcal{L}/N$ was applied on the resulting histograms.

According to fig. 6.1 electroweak background does not effect the measurement significantly. Even more interesting is the ratio between signal and background when only considering the low $p_\perp^Z$ region, where it is roughly 20000 : 1.

6.2. Conservative sideband estimation of QCD background

As Monte Carlo samples for QCD processes are costly to obtain on the one hand and don't necessarily describe data very well on the other hand, one needs to choose another method to estimate background effects from QCD.

There exist some data driven templating methods, which provide fake electrons from pure QCD processes to be used in the analysis and check the acceptance rate.

On the other hand, it might be sufficient to confirm that QCD effects are comparably small. Especially when it's clear, that other effects are likely to be of the order of 10 % it can be sufficient to show the QCD background effect to be about 1 %, for example.

A popular method for such an estimation is the sideband method. One chooses a well understood control observable, in our case it could be the invariant, reconstructed mass. It peaks comparably sharp and nearly all events should be contained in a window between, say, 66 GeV and 116 GeV. [27]

On the other hand, QCD background processes are not supposed to peak around some invariant mass, as the source for fake electrons is not the decay of an object with a certain mass. The assumption is then, that events outside the window can be considered as background. For the next step, preselection in RJE_TS might be relaxed to write out a wider Z mass window, here 50 GeV to 120 GeV are used, meaning that the so called *sidebands* have a total width of 20 GeV compared to the total width of 50 GeV for the signal region.

The selection in UEINVB can be changed to do an anti-cut on the reconstructed mass of the e^+e^- pair and trigger observables calculation and readout of the sidebands only. Resulting histograms have to be scaled according to the widths of the sideband and the signal band, in here it is a factor of 2.5.

With this method we find a *conservative* estimate, as we consider everything outside the mass window as backgrounds, which is overestimation. But, we find the total effect to be about 1.6 %, so anyways it can be considered small, compared to unfolding uncertainty and statistical limitations when requiring $p_{\perp}^Z < 3$ GeV. In the latter case, requiring the $p_{\perp}^Z$ cut, the total effect of QCD, however, decreases to 1.4 %.

What is more is the shape of the observables, which is similar between signal and QCD background obtained this way, see event shape plots in fig. 6.1. This again can be interpreted as overestimating the background, as many events selected like this do not only behave like signal, but in fact are signal.

6.3. Pileup influence estimation and correction procedure

As formerly mentioned, *pileup* is the occurrence of (1) additional independent scatters of multiple pairs of incoming protons within the same bunch crossing or (2) recording of events from the crossing just before (or after) due to time resolution issues in the detector.

Pileup itself can then be classified as in-time pileup and bunch-train pileup, which are more or less self explaining given the last paragraph.

As the analysis measures tracks, most of the pileup tracks can be rejected by requiring small

distance to the primary vertex (z_0, d_0 cut). This works sufficiently well as the probability for false positives decreases quadratically¹ with separation.

Additionally, ATHENA assigns reconstructed tracks to vertices and categorises latter to be *primary* or *pileup*. Tracks not mapped to the primary vertex can be rejected from the analysis. False assignment is an issue to be discussed and quantified, but this is not topic of the thesis.

The more problematic aspect of pileup is the vertex reconstruction resolution, which leads to merged vertices. In this case, the primary vertex with the hard subprocess cannot be separated from additional vertices due to pileup. Thus, the following sections try to estimate the probability of having a primary vertex merged with a pileup vertex and to develop a method to correct for pileup.

6.3.1. Probability of merged primary vertices

Extracting the merging probability function

Event reconstruction within ATHENA provides identification of primary and pileup vertices and their respective positions within the ATLAS detector coordinate system. As the thickness of the beams is small, only longitudinal positions z will be taken into account in this approach.

Figure 6.2. – Distribution of primary (**left**) and pileup (**right**) vertices from 2011 data. Fits with Gaussian (**left**) and sum of two Gaussians (**right**).

¹For this consider some hit area, represented by z_0, d_0 around the primary vertex, and its projection on a sphere around a pileup vertex. The radius of the sphere is the distance to the primary vertex, such that the surface of this sphere increases quadratically with the distance, whereas the hit area stays constant. From isotropy arguments one then finds that the probability to *hit* the primary vertex decreases quadratically.

Figure 6.2 shows the vertex distribution in z . For primary vertices a Gaussian is assumed and the fit yields a distribution function $\tilde{n}_{\text{Pri}}(z) = \tilde{A} \exp(-0.5 \cdot ((z - \tilde{z})/\sigma)^2)$ with $\tilde{A} \approx 3.6 \cdot 10^3$, $\tilde{z} \approx -5.0$ mm, $\sigma \approx 55.9$ mm. Normalising this in order to get unity when integrating over the whole area leads to $n_{\text{Pri}}(z) = \tilde{n}_{\text{Pri}}(z) / \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{n}_{\text{Pri}}(y) dy$, which effectively only decreases the maximum $\tilde{A} \rightarrow A \approx 7.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$. $n_{\text{Pri}}(z)$ is the *probability density function* (p.d.f.) to find a primary vertex at position z .

The same approach for pileup vertices fails. The Gaussian is too large in the centre while the tails are fitted very well. This might come from vertex merging between pileup vertices, as this lowers the number of detected, separable vertices especially in the central region. The effect is not huge, but for a good χ^2 value the sum of two Gaussians is used, which fits really nice:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{n}_{\text{PU}}(z) &= \tilde{B}_1 e^{-0.5 \cdot ((z - \tilde{z}_1^{\text{PU}})/\sigma_1^{\text{PU}})^2} + \tilde{B}_2 e^{-0.5 \cdot ((z - \tilde{z}_2^{\text{PU}})/\sigma_2^{\text{PU}})^2} & (6.1) \\ \tilde{B}_1 &\approx 5.89 \cdot 10^4 & \tilde{z}_1^{\text{PU}} &\approx -5.58 \text{ mm} & \sigma_1^{\text{PU}} &\approx 65.1 \text{ mm} \\ \tilde{B}_2 &\approx 5.29 \cdot 10^4 & \tilde{z}_2^{\text{PU}} &\approx -5.62 \text{ mm} & \sigma_2^{\text{PU}} &\approx 65.8 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

Transforming the fit function to a p.d.f. by normalising to 1 yields $n_{\text{PU}}(z)$. $n_{\text{PU}}(z)$ is the probability density, to find a pileup vertex in an event with exactly one pileup vertex at position z .

Furthermore the distribution of distances between the primary vertex and the pileup vertices, $\Delta = z - z_{\text{PV}}$ can be discussed. This is considered a Gaussian distribution as well, being constructed from the distributions of the two vertex types. But the distribution in figure 6.3 has a *dip* in the central region, which is caused by vertex merging.

$$N_{\text{PU}}(\Delta) = \tilde{C}_1 e^{-0.5 \cdot ((\Delta - \tilde{\Delta}_1)/\sigma_{\Delta})^2} - \underbrace{\tilde{C}_2 e^{-0.5 \cdot ((\Delta - \tilde{\Delta}_2)/\sigma_{\text{merge}})^2}}_{\tilde{m}(\Delta)} \quad (6.2)$$

An overall fit with a Gaussian for the tails in addition to a negative valued Gaussian for the central region (eq. (6.2)) is performed. The result for $\tilde{m}$ can be normalised to $m(\Delta)$ such that $m(\Delta = 0) = 1$. $m(\Delta)$ then represents the probability density for two vertices to get merged, when their distance is Δ . Two vertices at the same position are always merged.

Probability for a primary vertex to get merged

The probability density $m(\Delta)$ for two vertices to get merged given their distance is known, and so the probability density for a primary vertex at position z to get merged, $M(z)$ can be

Figure 6.3. – Distribution of distances between primary vertex and pileup vertices, $z - z_{PV}$. The distribution is fitted with a positive valued, broad Gaussian and a negative valued, thin Gaussian in the central region, which characterises the *merging probability* for a pileup vertex in the vicinity of the primary vertex.

written as:

$$M(z) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz' n_{PU}(z') m(z' - z) \quad (6.3)$$

As this represents a convolution of Gaussians, $M(z)$ is a Gaussian as well.

Probability for an event to contain a merged primary vertex

For one pileup vertex in each event, the probability for the primary vertex to be merged can naturally be defined as:

$$p = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz M(z) n_{Pri}(z) \approx 0.02 \quad (6.4)$$

In here, the merging probability at position z is multiplied by the probability to find the primary vertex at this position and finally integrated over all possible positions.

This probability is not valid for a number of pileup vertices different from 1. But, as mentioned in section 3.7, multiple simultaneous scatters occurred, such that the average of the total number of interactions per event record is about $\langle \mu \rangle = 5$.

Assuming a *Poissonian* distribution for the number of vertices with mean $\langle \mu \rangle = 5$ per event

gives the probability for an event to have i pileup vertices as $P(i, \langle \mu \rangle - 1)$, in addition to the primary vertex.

Merging itself can be modelled by a *Poissonian* as well. In an event with i pileup vertices, the probability to have a non-merged primary vertex is given as $P(0, i p)$.

As $P(i, 4)$ and $P(0, i p)$ are independent, the conditional probability $A = P(0 | \langle \mu \rangle = 5)$ to have a non-merged primary vertex for an average number of 5 interactions per event record is given by:

$$A = P(0 | \langle \mu \rangle = 5) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} P(i, 4) P(0, i p)}{\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} P(i, 4)} \quad (6.5)$$

$$\approx \underline{\underline{0.92}} =: 1 - \bar{A} \quad (6.6)$$

Result

The total number of events with polluted primary vertices can roughly be estimated as $\bar{A} \approx 8\%$, which cannot be neglected in the further analysis.

Thus, the following sections will illustrate what the actual effects on the observables are and whether they can be ignored or treated within the overall unfolding or need a distinct correction obtained for each observable separately.

6.3.2. Estimation of pileup effects on observables

Pileup, in contrast to background from event selection, does not change the actual number of events, but observables measured within an event itself. This means, that migration between bins in the observables due to added pileup have to be examined and understood.

For this examination two principle different effects can be observed, which are illustrated in figure 6.4. One is a smearing, which results from *undirectional*² additional tracks, leading to a broadening of the diagonal in the smearing matrix. The other is a directional change, influencing similar events always in the same kind.

The first effect leads to uncertainties to be added to the measured bin value, whereas the second also leads to shifts.

The question is now how to face this problem and invert the smearing and the shift. As there is a variety of possibilities, only some of them can be discussed in this thesis. A comparison

²Undirectional is meant to result *omnidirectional* on the final observables. The added tracks themselves are for sure somehow *directional*.

Figure 6.4. – Two scenarios of pileup influence on measured observable bins. **Left:** Smearing. Omnidirectional change due to pileup merging. Several *truth* bins contribute to the same *measured* bin (**red**) and the other way around (**green**). The mean values are not significantly changed (**red** $\approx$ **green**). **Right:** Shift. Added tracks lead to directional changes. In this example $\langle \text{measured} \rangle > \langle \text{true} \rangle$.

between the results might give a hint on the systematic error made when choosing one of the methods.

One idea is to let the overall unfolding of detector effects take the pileup effect into account. As this method gets *trained* with the migration from generator truth to reconstruction after full detector simulation with added pileup, this inversion should be possible in principle. However, it is welcome to disentangle components of systematic errors as much as possible, meaning to treat pileup and detector effects separately.

Another idea is a bin-to-bin unfolding, meaning the direct comparison between bin contents with and without pileup. This means to obtain correction factors and their uncertainties for each bin to apply them during a certain step of the data analysis. Whether this should be done before or after detector unfolding, that is on reconstruction level or on unfolded/generator level is not obvious a-priori. Therefore, for the final analysis, both paths need to be followed in order to show that they yield comparable results.

A fully MC-based method of obtaining correction factors to be applied when processing reconstructed events is described in section 6.3.4, whereas two data driven approaches are presented in 6.3.5 and 6.3.6. The overall unfolding method is not discussed in this thesis.

Bin-to-bin unfolding only accounts for projections to the axes in figure 6.4, not for migration between the bins. More sophisticated unfolding methods, which make use of these additional information, are on the market. Some of them are discussed in [40, 45, 46] and

might be applied later on, but will not be used in here for demonstration.

6.3.3. Strategy for obtaining correction factors

Methods discussed here are based on bin-to-bin unfolding correction factors as described for example in [40].

Given two histograms for the same observable, one with *plain* information and the other with smeared and shifted information, are denoted as $\vec{\nu}$ and $\vec{\mu}$. In figure 6.4 the first would be the projection on the abscissa, whereas the latter would the projection on the ordinate. Now, correction factors C_i have to be found, such that the measured value gets transformed to the true one, i.e.

$$\nu_i = C_i \mu_i. \quad (6.7)$$

The correction factor in this method is simply the ratio between true and measured value, $C_i = \nu_i / \mu_i$. Given the values are very large, but nevertheless statistically limited, one might assume $\sigma_i^\nu \approx \sqrt{\nu_i}$ and $\sigma_i^\mu \approx \sqrt{\mu_i}$. Assuming a high correlation (i.e. correlation coefficient $\rho \approx 1$) between ν_i and μ_i , for example only a small percentage of the events contains merged vertices, the uncertainty of C_i can be calculated as follows:

$$\sigma^{C_i} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{dC_i}{d\nu_i} \sigma_i^\nu\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dC_i}{d\mu_i} \sigma_i^\mu\right)^2 + \frac{dC_i}{d\nu_i} \sigma_i^\nu \frac{dC_i}{d\mu_i} \sigma_i^\mu \rho} \quad (6.8)$$

$$= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_i^\nu}{\mu_i}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\nu_i \sigma_i^\mu}{\mu_i^2}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_i^\nu}{\mu_i} \frac{\nu_i \sigma_i^\mu}{\mu_i^2} \rho} \quad (6.9)$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{\nu_i}{\mu_i^2} + \frac{\nu_i^2}{\mu_i^3} - \frac{\nu_i^{3/2}}{\mu_i^{5/2}} \rho} \quad (6.10)$$

It might be further useful, to relate the correction factor to the statistical uncertainty. If the statistical uncertainty is larger than the correction factor values, latter can simply be treated as systematic uncertainties.

But, if the correction factors are large compared to the uncertainties, a correction is more useful, as one is interested in presenting small overall errors.

6.3.4. Monte Carlo based estimation

MC based estimations require a good understanding of the processes under consideration. This involves detector behaviour as well as the structure of the pileup events in this case.

Figure 6.5. – Correction factors obtained from PYTHIA 6 sample on reconstruction level after full simulation with and without added PYTHIA 8 minimum bias events as pileup. Only statistical errors shown, according to eq. (6.10). Central error band shows statistical uncertainty of pileup histogram only.

As full detector simulations take a very long time, it is not feasible to generate more samples during the work for this thesis. In the present case, only one data sample is known to be generated with and without pileup in full reconstruction mode, which is the PYTHIA 6 sample listed in table 5.1.

Pileup is added as pre-calculated hits³ during the reconstruction step, distributed in the detector as it was expected for early 2011 data taking and the respective instantaneous luminosity.

In figure 6.5 these correction factors obtained by dividing the respective bin contents of a sample with pileup by a sample without pileup are shown. The original histograms can be found in figure 5.1 on page 37. Additionally, they are compared to the statistical error in the histogram with pileup simulation, which would correspond to the measured observable.

The plots contain the following statements.

First, low multiplicities are underrepresented in samples with pileup. This can be seen directly in N_{trk} . This is an expected influence of added tracks due to pileup.

Second, one also finds that pileup influences extremal values for event shapes. Consider, for example, the high thrust region, adding pileup leads to a decrease of thrust, which corresponds to a more spherical and isotropic event. The same behaviour can be seen in the low minor region and also low sphericity and F-parameter.

The result is a clear shift, whereas the spread, meaning the error of the correction factor, is comparably small in regions with good statistics.

Correction factors are of the order of up to 5 % in the central regions with good statistics, and even up to 10 % and larger (for N_{trk}) in extremal, and low stats regions.

As a consequence, one would try to correct for that effect rather than adding a rather large systematic error band around the results.

6.3.5. Data driven estimation (one step method)

Another approach to obtain correction factors can be made without any model assumptions on Monte Carlo by purely using data. In this case one relies on the vertexing algorithm of ATHENA, for which the uncertainties have to be studied in any case.

The idea is to add tracks from a pileup vertex into a selected primary vertex and calculate the change in the event shapes resulting from this virtual *merge*. For this, one can build up a pileup track library from data, taking for example vertices reasonably separated (here:

³After the event generation step a detector simulation is performed, which results in *hits* in the detector components. A certain class of events, so called *minimum bias events* with a very high cross section, are modelled very well by PYTHIA 8 and used as pileup estimation. As the detector simulation is a rather costly process, pileup is added by appending *hits* from this sample after the detector simulation step for the signal sample.

Figure 6.6. – Correction factors obtained from additionally, virtually merged vertices in a data driven method. Only statistical errors shown. Central error band shows statistical uncertainty of virtually merged histogram only.

$z - z^{\text{Pri}} > 10 \text{ mm}$) from the primary vertex, applying the same cuts as for selected primary vertex' tracks, $d_0^{\text{Pri}}, z_0^{\text{Pri}}$ cuts excluded.

In the analysis stage described in section 4.2 and figure 4.1, one simply adds tracks from a randomly picked pileup vertex out of the library to the *selected tracks container*. This can either be done in every event, when later on accounting for the fraction of events for which the primary vertex does not get merged ($\bar{A}$, see section 6.3.1), or only in a certain fraction A of events.

Results are stored in a 2d histogram (ROOT: :TH2) as so called *smearing matrix*, showing the *true* value before and the *measured* value after added tracks.

To fill the histograms, at least two different methods can be used. The one utilises $M(z)$ (probability for a primary vertex in position z to get merged, see eq. (6.3)) and only adds tracks with a certain probability. This should yield the correct result in any case, but needs a higher number of total events to populate the smearing matrix.

The other assumes the bin in the observable is not depending on the position of the merged vertex, which should hold at least as a first estimate. Knowing this, one can simply merge vertices for every event, which leads to a broader, but much better populated migration matrix. In the last step of the preparation of the migration matrix one can now reason that only $\bar{A} \approx 8\%$ (see results of section 6.3.1) are merged, so 92% should hold *identity* in the smearing matrix.

Be $n(i, j)$ the content of the (i, j) -bin, where i numbers the bins on the *unmerged* and j on the *merged* axis. Technically, one than increases the diagonal bins

$$n(i, i) = n(i, i) + \frac{\bar{A}}{A} \cdot \sum_j n(i, j), \quad \forall i. \quad (6.11)$$

Additionally, an estimation of the error of $\frac{\bar{A}}{A}$ can be propagated to $n(i, i)$ and to the final correction factors. However, here only first order corrections are applied to give an idea of the effect.

From there on, one can use the smearing matrix for unfolding according to *Bayes theorem* [45, 46] or to obtain correction factors as described earlier in this chapter.

Figure 6.6 shows the results of the correction factor method. For comparison the statistical error of the virtual *measurement* is also shown. The correction factors show the same characteristics as figure 6.5, but are smoother and show higher statistics.

Also there are some little discrepancies, which can be caused by assumptions made in the virtual merging method. At first, it might merge an already merged primary vertex with an additional pileup vertex, and this behaviour might differ from a pure underlying event vertex

getting merged. But, even if it is like this, it should result in an error of the order of the total expected number of already merged vertices times the chance for them to get merged, so the effect on the correction factor should be $\leq \mathcal{O}(0.6\%)$.

At second, it is assumed that the z position of the primary vertex is not correlated to the event shape calculated. This seems not to hold fully. One might assume, that central vertices are more well defined than peripheral ones. This could lead to not fully reconstruct vertices in the high- $|z|$ region such that they have less tracks and e.g. higher thrust values. This is a problem of vertexing and shall be discussed connected to vertexing issues.

These two effects may also amplify each other as centrally, well defined vertices are more likely to be already merged beforehand, and vice versa.

6.3.6. Data driven estimation (HBOM)

A rather new unfolding method in the ATLAS softQCD working group is the *bit backspace once more* (HBOM) method, internally presented by *James Monk* [47].

Assuming data is obtained at a stage where a certain effect is already applied once. In the case discussed in this thesis this would represent the reconstruction level with merged vertices. The systematic effect is well known. Pileup interactions are distributed randomly in the detector and sometimes merge with the primary vertex.

This can be applied subsequently with the respective probability. In the systematics loop of UEINVB this would mean to not only ask one time, whether the probability to have a merged vertex exceeds a random number, but ask N times.

The final observable bins then can be seen as functions of N . With $N = 0$ being the original recorded data, $N = 1$ with one additional merge attempt, and so on. With the help of the PROFESSOR tool, a bin-wise interpolation can be built. From this interpolation by polynomials of n -th order ($n < N$) an extrapolated estimation for $N = -1$ can be calculated, which should represent a state without the systematic applied for the first time. In our case, this would mean to have removed the effects of merged vertices due to pileup.

The systematic error of this method can be estimated by using a higher polynomial representation. Statistical errors can be propagated through the interpolation by *simply* varying the bin contents according to their respective standard deviation. Performing the interpolation M times and take the envelope of the inner 68% should give an estimate of the standard deviation due to statistical uncertainties in the extrapolated bins.

The method is illustrated in figure 6.7 where the evolutions of N_{trk} and transverse thrust ($T_{\perp,g}$) when adding more and more pileup are shown. The results are relative event weights represented by the blue lines, which can be applied during unfolding.

Figure 6.7. - N_{trk} (**top**) and transverse thrust ($T_{\perp,g}$, **bottom**) as examples for the *HBOM* method. Successively adding vertices with a certain probability A creates the spectrum. The **blue** line is the back-interpolation obtained with PROFESSOR. The ratio plots of the **blue** line with respect to *nominal* are the correction factors.

Transverse Thrust

Figure 6.8. – *Closure test*, PYTHIA 6 samples with and without pileup in reconstruction (see table 5.1) as well as PYTHIA 6 sample with pileup after applying corrections obtained from *HBOM* method. Only statistical errors on PYTHIA 6 samples shown.

A first attempt to measure the performance of this method can be seen in figure 6.8. Correction factors obtained from data with the back-extrapolation method are applied on a MC sample with pileup and compared to a MC sample without pileup. The agreement is quite promising.

7. Results

In the domain of *underlying event* physics, one common model for *multiple parton interactions* is described. Parameters in this model as well as their influence on modelled physics are explained (chapter 2). By the usage of *Monte Carlo* simulations, which have been introduced in short, it is possible to also illustrate the parameter dependency of the models. Therefore, observables which are thought to exhibit high dependency on the model parameters - *event shapes* - are defined.

The analysis framework which operates directly on generator level, consisting of RIVET and PROFESSOR, is used to analyse sensitivities of observables to the model parameters. The respective chapter also includes an attempt to define *sensitivity* in an intuitive way. In order to perform the sensitivity study, a RIVET analysis has been written. Also, PROFESSOR was modified to fit the definition of sensitivity and also to allow for polynomials of arbitrary order to be used in interpolations.

After having established sensitivity in principle, an experimental approach to measure the observables discussed beforehand is described. The ATLAS detector at the LHC as well as its operational conditions are discussed (chapter 3).

An analysis chain, that operates on data taken with the ATLAS detector in early 2011, has been set up and is presented in a detailed, technical manner (chapter 4). First results on reconstruction level, without applying corrections to data, are shown (chapter 5). On the one hand, the overall picture between observables in MC compared to data looks promising. On the other hand, however, there is a large discrepancy for extremal values in a certain phase space. But, this also looks very promising, as a first evidence for limitations of current models might be found.

Further steps to produce data to a level that is corrected for detector effects are outlined. The estimation of backgrounds from different processes as well as considerations concerning pileup are included in this thesis (chapter 6). For the latter a variety of approaches is listed, a selection of them is performed. A *closure test* between MC with and without modelled pileup and the applied correction is presented in the very last section. It looks very promising to be able to correct for effects due to pileup and be able to find even better models for the *underlying event*, based on the measurement outlined in this thesis.

A. SHERPA Run.dat

```
(run){
  EVENTS = 1000000
  ANALYSIS = Rivet
  ANALYSIS_OUTPUT = out.aida
}(run)
(beam){
  BEAM_1 = 2212; BEAM_ENERGY_1 = 3500;
  BEAM_2 = 2212; BEAM_ENERGY_2 = 3500;
  K_PERP_MEAN_1 = <__K_PERP_MEAN__>;
  K_PERP_SIGMA_1 = <__K_PERP_SIGMA__>;
  K_PERP_MEAN_2 = <__K_PERP_MEAN__>;
  K_PERP_SIGMA_2 = <__K_PERP_SIGMA__>;
}(beam)
(processes){
  Process 93 93 -> -11 11
  Order_EW 2;
  CKKW sqr(30/E_CMS)
  End process;
}(processes)
(selector){
  Mass -11 11 50 130
}(selector)
(me){
  ME_SIGNAL_GENERATOR = Internal Comix
}(me)
(mi){
  MI_HANDLER = Amisic
  PROFILE_FUNCTION = Double_Gaussian;
  PROFILE_PARAMETERS = <__PROFILE_PARAMETERS_1__> <__PROFILE_PARAMETERS_2__>;
  SCALE_MIN = <__SCALE_MIN__>;
  RESCALE_EXPONENT = <__RESCALE_EXPONENT__>;
}(mi)
(analysis){
  BEGIN_RIVET {
    -a MC_EVENTSHAPES_500
  } END_RIVET
}(analysis)
```

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